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IMPROVING THE METHOD OF ASSESSING MARKETING ACTIVITY EFFICIENCY IN SEWING AND KNITTING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article examines the issue of improving the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of marketing activities in textile enterprises and developing practical recommendations for increasing marketing efficiency. The study is based on the Balanced Scorecard system, which is widely used in international practice. The proposed approach makes it possible to evaluate marketing activities more comprehensively by taking into account financial, customer, internal process, and learning and growth indicators.

Keywords: marketing, marketing activity, effectiveness, efficiency, evaluation method, marketing management, Balanced Scorecard.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования методики оценки эффективности маркетинговой деятельности на предприятиях текстильной промышленности и разработки практических рекомендаций по повышению её результативности. Исследование основано на применении системы сбалансированных показателей (Balanced Scorecard), широко используемой в международной практике. Предлагаемый подход позволяет комплексно оценивать эффективность маркетинговой деятельности с учетом финансовых показателей, удовлетворенности потребителей, внутренних бизнес-процессов, а также факторов обучения и развития персонала.

Ключевые слова: маркетинг, маркетинговая деятельность, эффективность, результативность, методика оценки, управление маркетингом, система сбалансированных показателей.

INTRODUCTION

The current state of the global market and its future development prospects confirm that only goods and services with high competitiveness, quality, and added value can ensure stable and long-term market positions. Therefore, under conditions of strong competition in the global market, every manufacturing enterprise and entrepreneur should regularly conduct research aimed at creating new types of products, improving existing products, and entering new market segments. In this process, it is important to study market conditions and consumer behavior, develop an effective marketing strategy based on market-oriented research, and successfully implement it. This is one of the key conditions for business development and long-term prosperity.

At the same time, this issue requires a macroeconomic approach to ensure the rapid entry of national producers into the world market. Every country is interested in supporting the active participation of domestic producers of goods and services in international markets and strengthening their position in competitive segments. This requires the state to consistently develop measures aimed at creating the necessary conditions, providing practical support, and ensuring the legal protection of local entrepreneurs whose activities contribute to the country's international trade volume, export potential, sustainable economic growth, and innovative development.

In this regard, serious attention is being paid to the development of the cotton and textile complex in Uzbekistan. A number of measures have been developed and implemented to support the further development of the textile industry at the state level. These measures are reflected in presidential decrees, resolutions, and decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers adopted in recent years. In particular, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 sets the task of “doubling the volume of textile industry production” [1].

Ensuring the effective implementation of these tasks requires the development of measures aimed at further improving the effectiveness of marketing activities. This, in turn, makes it necessary to improve the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of marketing activities of textile industry enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan and to apply it in practice.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The problem of determining marketing effectiveness is currently considered one of the complex issues that has not yet been sufficiently developed from a methodological perspective. Therefore, in the scientific literature, various approaches and interpretations have been proposed regarding the concept of marketing effectiveness, its calculation formulas, and assessment methodology.

A method for the rapid analysis of enterprise marketing activities using indicators such as market size, order portfolio, competition, sales volume, and advertising costs was proposed by Russian scholars S. V. Besfamilnaya and A. A. Ryzhov [2]. Another Russian researcher, E. Patrusheva, proposed an integrated methodology that describes the marketing service of an enterprise through its organizational position. However, the main limitation of this method is the subjective assessment of certain features of marketing activities [3]. R. G. Guchetel studied the issue of improving marketing management in industrial enterprises based on the use of the Balanced Scorecard [4]. Among Uzbek scholars, A. Sh. Bekmurodov developed a methodology based on a target-oriented approach to assessing marketing effectiveness [5].

The practical application of existing methods for determining marketing effectiveness creates certain difficulties, particularly in separating profits and expenses into individual components for calculation purposes. This indicates the need to further improve the methodology for assessing marketing effectiveness.

The analysis of research works devoted to the assessment of marketing effectiveness shows that most developments in this area are related to management systems, branding, business processes, and marketing. A. I. Kovalev defines effectiveness as “the degree of implementation of policy and achievement of qualitative goals, including the degree of satisfaction of consumer needs and prospects through the implementation of planned activities and the achievement of planned results” [6]. In her work on branding effectiveness, O. N. Alkanova describes this concept as the degree of achievement of the target values of the main indicators characterizing a brand’s activity in the market [7].

O. V. Kitova defines marketing effectiveness as “the most effective way to achieve marketing goals under conditions of alternative resource use”. She also emphasizes that marketing management should include “the formation of a marketing strategy in the form of a system of measurable strategic goals, initiatives, and key performance indicators” [8]. O. K. Oyner expressed the opinion that the category of “marketing effectiveness” includes marketing productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness [9].

In our opinion, the effectiveness of the marketing system should be understood as the degree to which the achieved results correspond to the objectives set for attaining a specific goal, that is, the planned results.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on the scientific findings of foreign and local scholars related to the assessment of marketing activity efficiency. In the course of the study, statistical analysis, comparative analysis, expert evaluation, the Balanced Scorecard system, and assessment methods based on an integral indicator were used. These methods made it possible to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of marketing activities in sewing and knitting enterprises and to develop scientifically grounded recommendations for improving marketing management.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the practice of industrial enterprises in developed countries, the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) is widely used to assess enterprise performance [10]. However, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, this system has not yet been sufficiently applied in practice. The results of our marketing research show that many managers of sewing and knitting enterprises still do not have sufficient knowledge of the Balanced Scorecard: 36% of respondents are familiar with this system, while only 7.8% have used it in practice.

Therefore, the application of this system in the planning and management of enterprises that are part of the “Uztextile Industry” Association of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be considered highly effective.

In this study, the methodology for assessing marketing effectiveness based on a system of balanced indicators aimed at ensuring the achievement of the strategic goals of sewing and knitting enterprises has been improved. This represents an important step toward increasing the efficiency of the management system of enterprises included in the “Uztextile Industry” Association, as well as improving the activities of the Association as a whole.

In the study, an improved method for managing the effectiveness of marketing activities based on the Balanced Scorecard for a specific business area is proposed (Figure 1). This method can contribute to the further development of enterprises included in the “Uztextile Industry” Association under current challenging economic conditions. The implementation of the proposed method for improving marketing management

effectiveness in textile enterprises on the basis of the Balanced Scorecard should be carried out through the stages presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Marketing performance management method¹

¹ Author's development.

Stage 1. Determining the purpose of the marketing effectiveness management method. At this stage, the need to improve the method is substantiated based on the results of studying the current state of marketing effectiveness assessment in sewing and knitting enterprises.

Stage 2. Analysis of marketing activities of sewing and knitting enterprises. In order to develop a marketing effectiveness management method for sewing and knitting enterprises, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth analysis of the external and internal environment of the enterprise using modern analytical methods, including SWOT analysis, PEST analysis, GAP analysis, SPACE analysis, and other methods [11].

Stage 3. Determining the strategic goals of sewing and knitting enterprises. Strategic goals are usually long-term in nature. The strategic goals of sewing and knitting enterprises are determined based on the results of the analysis of the external and internal environment conducted at the previous stage through marketing research. These goals include future strategic directions related to the market, product, consumers, and competitors.

Stage 4. Creating a base of indicators for the introduction of the Balanced Scorecard. In order to introduce the Balanced Scorecard into the practice of textile enterprises, the above stages should be implemented through the following measures: assigning the relevant department the task of monitoring and summarizing the comprehensive application of this system and analyzing its results; clearly identifying the departments of the enterprise where the BSC will be introduced; determining the methods for providing information by the departments responsible for the introduction of the BSC; and strictly monitoring the implementation process. In particular, it is necessary to ensure the complete elimination of delays and errors identified in the enterprise's activities as a result of the implementation of this system [12].

It is important to note that the Balanced Scorecard should not be understood only as a tool for developing the financial plan and budget of an enterprise. Rather, this system provides effective results when the indicators formed on its basis are properly analyzed, evaluated, planned, and controlled.

Stage 5. Development of a marketing strategy. In strategic management, the clear definition of a strategy is an important factor determining the quality of an enterprise's long-term development. Based on the construction of the Balanced Scorecard, it becomes possible to clarify the following aspects that ensure the quality of an enterprise's strategy:

- which internal and external factors should be taken into account when developing the strategy;
- what strengths and weaknesses the enterprise has compared with its competitors;
- what financial capabilities and human resource potential the enterprise has for implementing a particular strategy;
- which aspects of production activity should receive greater attention when developing the strategy.

As a result, the introduction of the Balanced Scorecard system into the traditional processes of developing and implementing a strategy makes it possible to increase the efficiency of textile enterprise management. This approach is based on the principle "from strategy to action" and supports the development of a success plan grounded in performance indicators and key influencing factors. Accordingly, it creates opportunities to improve management mechanisms and increase the level of profitability. For this purpose, a strategic map of the Balanced Scorecard system is developed for the textile enterprise.

Stage 6. Calculation of an integral indicator of marketing performance management. Based on the strategic map of the Balanced Scorecard system, an integral indicator of marketing performance management is calculated. This makes it possible to determine the level of implementation of each marketing lever, or perspective, and to calculate the final indicator reflecting the effectiveness of marketing activities. It also helps identify which components of marketing activity require greater attention in order to improve marketing efficiency in sewing and knitting enterprises.

Each current marketing objective is assigned a priority level, A_i . Then, using the expert evaluation method, the level of implementation in the short term is assessed on a scale from 1 to 5 points, where $B_{\max} = 5$. After that, the actual integral score, $\sum A_i V_i$, and the maximum possible planned score, $\sum A_i V_{\max}$, are calculated. Based on these data, the level of implementation of each perspective is determined using the ratio $\sum A_i V_i / \sum A_i V_{\max}$, and the final indicator characterizing the implementation of marketing activities is identified.

Stage 7. Evaluation of marketing effectiveness. Indicator-based assessment is used to calculate the actual value of marketing effectiveness based on the reporting period data. Figure 2 presents the algorithm for evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Detailed assessment of the effectiveness of marketing tasks²

I – prospects; J – objectives; N – number of prospects; M – number of objectives; MD – marketing activities.

It is also necessary to compare the results obtained and identify the causes of deviations. In this dissertation research, the Harrington scale is used as a basis for assessing the effectiveness of marketing performance management, which allows determining the level of importance of marketing indicators (Table 1).

Table 1
Harrington’s marketing performance assessment scale

Value	Content description of the level of marketing activity performance indicators
0,8–1,0	Very high level of MF performance
0,64–0,8	High level of MF performance
0,37–0,64	Average level of MF performance
0,2–0,37	Low level of MF performance
0,0–0,2	Very low level of MF performance

Step 8. Development of recommendations for increasing the effectiveness of marketing activities. The final stage is the determination of actions to improve the effectiveness of marketing activities (Table 2).

² Muallif ishlanmasi.

Table 2
Actions that can increase the effectiveness of marketing activities³

Value	Direction of movement
0,8–1,0	Marketing activities are highly effective. Warning actions are required. If effectiveness = 1, then it is necessary to maintain this level of activity, increase the standard, or reduce resources to achieve the objectives.
0,64–0,8	Marketing activities are effective, but minor corrections are needed.
0,37–0,64	The marketing activities were almost effective and the objectives were partially achieved. Corrective action is required, as well as reallocation of resources.
0,2–0,37	Marketing activities are ineffective and require significant corrective action. Additional tasks should be defined to achieve the goal.
0,0–0,2	Marketing activities are ineffective, objectives are not being achieved, and significant changes and development of marketing activities are required. If the efficiency = 0, then marketing service should be organized in the enterprise.

The developed method for assessing the effectiveness of marketing activity management was applied to the activities of "BETLIS TEXTILE" LLC.

Stage 1. The purpose of implementing this method for managing the effectiveness of marketing activities is to improve the marketing system of "BETLIS TEXTILE" LLC, increase the efficiency of marketing investments, objectively assess the enterprise's marketing activities, and introduce this method among all employees of the enterprise.

Stage 2. The next stage involves analyzing the marketing activities of the enterprise. At this stage, the external and internal environmental factors identified through SWOT analysis were examined.

Stage 3. "BETLIS TEXTILE" LLC, as a sewing and knitting enterprise, applies several combined strategies, including product and customer strategies. The main directions of the product strategy are as follows:

managing and diversifying the product range;

developing a new product concept, since, in modern market conditions, continuous innovation in product development is a prerequisite for ensuring the sustainable operation of the enterprise.

The customer strategy is based on the development of a unified distribution system aimed at the successful promotion of products.

Stages 4–5. At these stages, it was proposed to identify the 30 most important strategic goals of the sewing and knitting enterprise based on expert evaluation, and the corresponding results were obtained.

Stage 6. Development of the Balanced Scorecard for marketing activities. The strategic goals of "BETLIS TEXTILE" LLC include updating the range of knitted products, increasing export potential, introducing new technologies into production, improving product quality, satisfying consumer demand and increasing customer loyalty, reducing the loss of profitable customers, promoting the brand, developing a unified distribution system, and expanding regional and foreign trade markets.

Based on the above, it is appropriate to distinguish the following perspectives of the enterprise's marketing activity for the development of the Balanced Scorecard (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Directions (prospects) for «BETLIS TEXTILE» LLC⁴

³ Author's development.

⁴ Author's development.

A table was developed for “BETLIS TEXTILE” LLC, reflecting strategic goals, operational marketing objectives, indicators, and the necessary measures for their implementation. Based on this table, human and financial resources were allocated, responsibilities for task implementation were distributed, and opportunities for managing marketing effectiveness by strengthening specific tasks were identified.

Step 7. Based on this table, it is possible to develop a model for managing the effectiveness of marketing activities by calculating an integral indicator required for developing measures to improve marketing effectiveness in “BETLIS TEXTILE” LLC. On the basis of the strategic map of the Balanced Scorecard system, the integral indicator of marketing effectiveness management is calculated, the level of implementation of each marketing lever, or perspective, is determined, and the final indicator is obtained. This indicator reflects the effectiveness of marketing activities and shows which components the sewing and knitting enterprise should pay greater attention to in order to increase marketing effectiveness.

Step 8. Based on the obtained results, graphs can be constructed to compare planned and actual results (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Effectiveness of marketing activity of «BETLIS TEKSTIL» LLC⁵

The data presented in Figure 4 show that “BETLIS TEXTILE” LLC achieved the highest level of marketing effectiveness in the “Product Distribution” and “Product” perspectives, at 80.0% and 76.66%, respectively. A slightly lower level was achieved in the “Customer Relations” perspective, at 70.0%. In the “Mobilization” perspective, the implementation level was 66.66%.

The data presented in Figure 4 show that “BETLIS TEXTILE” LLC achieved the highest level of marketing effectiveness in the “Product Distribution” and “Product” perspectives, at 80.0% and 76.66%, respectively. A slightly lower level of effectiveness was observed in the “Customer Relations” perspective, at 70.0%. In the “Mobilization” perspective, the implementation level reached 66.66%.

After analyzing all these indicators, the final integral indicator of marketing system effectiveness was calculated at 73.33%. According to the scale presented in Table 1, this result indicates that the management of marketing activity effectiveness at the sewing and knitting enterprise is at a “high” level.

At the same time, “BETLIS TEXTILE” LLC should pay greater attention to customer relations, improve marketing activities, and increase consumer loyalty. As a result, these measures will contribute to further improving the overall marketing effectiveness of the enterprise.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the obtained results, recommendations for improving the effectiveness of marketing activities can be proposed (Table 3).

⁵ Author's development.

Table 3
Recommendations for improving the effectiveness of marketing activities⁶

«BETLIS TEXTILE» LLC			
«Product»	«Customer Relations»	«MOVEMENT»	«DISTRIBUTION»
Marketing activities are effective, but at the same time, it is necessary to implement minor corrective actions.	Marketing activities are almost effective and goals are partially achieved. Repair work and a reallocation of resources is required.	Marketing activities are relatively efficient, requiring corrective actions and the search for new market segments.	Marketing activities are relatively efficient, requiring corrective actions and the search for new sales channels.

In general, it can be concluded that the Balanced Scorecard in marketing activities makes it possible to systematize strategic and operational planning processes. It provides the management of sewing and knitting enterprises with comprehensive information on the functioning of the marketing system, clearly explains the essence of strategic goals to all participants involved in strategy implementation, and ensures that the necessary and understandable information is separated from the enterprise's large information system.

By consistently implementing immediate tactical goals, a sewing and knitting enterprise gradually moves toward achieving its established strategic goals. In this way, a mechanism for managing the effectiveness of marketing activities in sewing and knitting enterprises can be successfully implemented.

The main challenge in developing a Balanced Scorecard for marketing activities is the complexity of determining appropriate measurement indicators. Nevertheless, the Balanced Scorecard remains an effective tool for implementing enterprise strategy and can contribute to the successful long-term development of the enterprise.

The proposed method for managing the effectiveness of marketing activities can serve as a methodological basis for enterprises in the sewing and knitting industry. However, before applying this method, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the enterprise's activities and clearly determine its business direction. This will make it possible to define more precisely the key perspectives, strategic and tactical goals, as well as the main directions for developing marketing activities.

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